

The Development of Participatory Model Between School and Community in Developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Center: A Case Study of Khoa Community, Lao Sub-District, Kosumphisai District, Maha Sarakham Province

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Abstract

The objectives of this research were : 1) to study the learning sources conditions of Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province by using Workshop of Tree Diagram, 2) to develop Participatory Model between schools and communities in developing Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers at Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province, and 3) to evaluate the usage of the developed Participation Model. The research design was Participatory Action Research (PAR) with 2 major processes: 1) 6 Steps of PAR, and 2) 15 Sub-activities of implementation in Participatory Learning Activities. The statistic used were average, mean, standard deviation and t-test (Dependent). The research instruments were 1) the model for implementation of Participation between schools and communities in developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers, and 2) the instruments for collecting data during and after use the model. The results were as follows: 1) there were 6 Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers in mixed agriculture in the areas that needed to developed to be ready for providing the learning activities. 2) The Participation Model between schools and communities in developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers, investigated by 5 experts, found that levels of feasibility, propriety, and utility were in the highest levels with the accuracy was in high level. 3) Local participations were able to do process of Participatory Learning Activity: 3.1) the efficiency of process was 89.62/85.90 as specified criterion, 3.2) the effectiveness index of overall development in Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers was 0.7494 which indicated that the managers of the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers were increased at 74.94 3.3) difference of the pre-test and post-test of knowledge and comprehension in leadership, Sufficiency Economy, and knowledge management was statistical significantly at .05, 3.4) the satisfaction on participation between schools and communities in development of Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers was at high level, and 3.5) there were competencies in participation in Sufficiency Economy Activities in approximation, reasonability, good immunity, knowledge condition, and ethics condition in highest level ($\bar{x} = 4.63$)

Introduction

Since Sukhothai period till the beginning of Ayutthaya period, learning management and Thai Society had related together as education started from home, temples, and the palace through parents, monks, and foreign teachers. At that time, learning management was in simple and suitable ways that people had been taught about the things that could be used within their daily lives. Thai education nowadays, with educational institutes and learning organizations that were orderly significant and associated, still not occurred only in schools but broadly narrated to societies; families, temples, industries, armies, economy, and mass media, for example. It meant that education was the way and aim of humans. In the future, learning management should be prepared for all people and should involve people in managing education. Learning management should not be managed only by instructors, educational institutes or the Ministry of Education, but every part should participate in managing education (Vasee, 2002, p.7-10).Runcharoen (2003) stated that schools were necessary and significant for managing education because they have offered education to all people.

Thai society has been affected from globalization. In the level of rural villages, capitalism obsessed villagers' way of life which caused semi-urban countryside society. There were various social problems occurring, people spent their time more on finding money for daily lives payments and for debt payments.

Therefore, there had been changed in their living. Agriculturalists had grown plants and rice only in the season of planting. Out of the season, they moved to work as unskilled labor in towns or other areas which meant that they left behind their families, their old age people and children, in the villages. Therefore, family members did not live together for months. The relationship in the family was decreased on contrast to the advancement of objects, basic structures, and technology that increased to all areas. It could be said that, since 40 years of Thailand's Planning developments, there has been damaged in village life management as villagers could not manage their own livings but the outsider people did. How would villagers gain their life's confidence back, and how would villagers get their families, communities, and their good communities health back? (PhongPhit et al, 2002, p. 11-12).

The philosophy of Sufficiency Economy from King Rama 9th, the best King of Thailand, seem to be the best way to apply to strengthen Thai people life management in balancing their society to be the 1) quality society, 2) knowledgeable society, and kindness society. His majesty the king had stated that individual or group of people should know, love, and cohesion. Know meant knowing what to do, knowing all factors, knowing about problems and knowing how to solve problems. Love meant love to do those knowing things, and cohesion meant participation working because we should have strong energy to achieve the purposes (Office of the Royal Development Projects Board, 2007, p. 32). This important and significant philosophy offered methods to solve problems that the world nowadays has been confronted; unstable economy, bad pollution, and global warming. (Chantarasombat, 2007, P. 269). Therefore, the philosophy should be used with definite policies, objectives, developing organizations, units, groups, local communities, and general users (Wattanasiritam, 2006, p. 11-12).

Thai education nowadays should focused on participation and using various learning sources because only learning from schools were not sufficient for developing young generation to manage their daily life's, working, culture, environment, and local resources. Moreover, learning from school only should made them lacking of their capabilities of living and their abilities on developing in their communities concerned since there were not enough diverse communities learning resources to support their studies. Wasri (2002, p. 21) mentioned that participation in learning could gain educational achievement because related people and others did learn together.

According to education reform in the Education Act B.E.2542 Section 4, it defined that education was the process of learning for person and society development through learning instructions, training, seminar, culture inheritance, advancement of academic knowledge, and continuous creation of learning conditions and factors of learning. State 8 of the Act also mentioned that learning management was the people's long life, and was the supportive important factor for learning directly. Since long live learning was the main point of learning management, various knowledge in communities seemed like the teaching and learning laboratories. Beside this, they provided other good benefits; learning expansions, long life learning, process of learning, and direct experiences. This could be said that long live learning was the steadily process to develop learning narrated to the country's learning management. (Department of Local Administration, 2005, p. 1-5).

The study of Luepanya (2012, p. 195-196) on conditions of Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers in 3 villages; Ban Wang Chan Moo 4, Ban Wang Mai, and Ban Wang Neu Moo 16, Naka Sub district, Wapi Pathum District, Maha Sarakham Province. There were 7 learning centers in the villages with various activities 1) mixed agriculture, 2) rice farming, 3) herbs planting, 4) rubber plantation, 5) tree planting, 6) domestication, and 7) fishery. The centers' managers still lacked of systematic management that they could not offer suitably advantages on educational knowledge. The centers lacked of landscape improvement, suitable services, the centers toilets, for examples. Hence, they could not manage the centers as learning sources for schools. The result related to the study of Kumphang (2014, p. 200-202) that do his study at Ku Kasing sub-district, Kaset Wisai district, Roi-et province with 6 learning centers; 1) intellectual of local silk, 2) New Theory agriculture, 3) local indigenous museum, 4) local literatures, 5) Khom archaeological site, and 6) Don Pu Ta. The centers could be managed as learning sources for schools but they lacked of systematic management to offer suitably advantages on educational knowledge. The centers had no landscape improvements, suitable services, the centers toilets, for examples. Moreover, they had no transferring indigenous knowledge from personal experiences to be explicit knowledge such as documents, publications, or mass media.

Participation between schools and community in managing the communities' learning center of Sufficiency Economy, both inside and outside schools, was important. The learning centers could offer various quality of learning that learners should be trained by investigating through their requirement, interesting and their talents to increase learning skills and ways to support their living. Thus, schools and communities in developing learning centers could offer diverse benefits to learners who could use the advantages suitably. Participation model seemed to be a reliable method that could be suitable with the conditions and environment results as shown in the study of Sacharung, Chantarasombat, and Yeamsang (2010, p. 125-127). Prathumchart (2010, p. 310-311) also studied how to develop a model of learning management in Chum Kam community by using both the participation action research and learning activities. The studies shown the process of participation in developing learning sources and learning management in community appropriately.

The researchers aimed to create the suitable participation model between the schools and communities in developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers at Khoa community, Lao Sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham Province in order to find a suitable and effective model of schools and communities participation in developing the centers with good relation on the process.

Research Questions

1. How was the condition of the Sufficiency Economy Learning Center at Khoa community, Lao Sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham Province?
2. What should be the suitable and effective model of participation between the school and community in developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Center at Khoa community, Lao Sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham Province?
3. How was the participants' satisfaction on the Participation Model between the school and community in developing the Self Efficiency Learning Center at Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province?

Research Objectives

1) To study the conditions of Sufficiency Economy Learning Center at Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province before using participating model between the school and community in developing Learning Center.

2) To develop a Participatory Model between the school and community in developing the Self Efficiency Learning Center at Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province.

3) To evaluate the use of the Participation Model between the school and community in developing the Self Efficiency Learning Center at Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province.

Significance of the Research

1) To recognize the conditions of Sufficiency Economy Learning Center at Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province before using the participating model between the school and community in developing Learning Center by using workshop of Tree Diagram,

2) To gain the Participatory Model between the school and community in developing the Self Efficiency Learning Center at Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province,

3) To recognize the participants' satisfaction on the process of the Participation Model between the school and community in developing the Self Efficiency Learning Center at Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province, and

4) To be a should-be model for other organizations to selected and applied in their areas.

Research Methodology

1. Research Area

The study was studied at Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham Province by purposive sampling technique. There are 4 schools in Lao sub-district; Yang Sin Chai Nong Hard School, Ban Tan Non Nong Khu School, Lao Nong Can School, and Ban Kwoa Sa-due Isan School, and there were 6 mixed Agricultural Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers in the area; 1) the Learning Center of Melientha suavis Pierre (Wild Phak-Wan of star gooseberry), 2) the Learning Center of short *Oroxylum indicum* (Lin Fah Tia), 3) the Learning Center of Coffee, 4) the Learning Center for Pig and Fish Raising, 5) the Learning Center of Sugar Cane and Cassava, and 6) the Learning Center of Organic Fertilizer where should be readiness in providing the learning activities. Though there were 11 villages in Lao sub-district, there were 2 villages, Ban Kwao and Ban Kwao Bung Kui, volunteered to attend the study. Only Ban Kwao Sa Due Isan School did volunteered to attend the study, too. Even though they were selected by volunteering, their responsive areas had various learning centers with continuously developing activities. However, the areas had no participation between the school and community. Beside this, indigenous knowledge people and/or community leaders in villages had diverse levels of knowledge, capabilities, skills, experiences, and culture which were suitable to the researchers to chose them to be the diversity participants.

2. Participants and the Researchers

The research participants were 26 persons of research principal investigators, and 19 persons of research additional ones as follows:

2.1 Groups of research principal investigators are 6 researchers and 20 co-investigators consisted of: 1) 1 school administrator, 2) 3 teachers of grade 4, 5, 6, 3) 6 managers of the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers, 4) 2 Village Headman and 2 of Assistant Village Headman, Moo 8, 9, and 5) 6 Purposive villagers of Moo 8, 9.

2.2 Group of 19 additional investigators consisted of: 1) 1 President of Lao Subdistrict Administrative Organization 2) 3 staff of Basic Education Committee 3) 15 representatives of students grade 4, 5 and 6.

3. Research Methodology

Research and Development technique focusing on participation action (Chantarasombat, 2008) was used with the following steps: 1) studying the conditions and problems then defining the developing topics, 2) creating team and developing ability, 3) planning, 4) processing and developing, 5) assessing and making summarize, and 6) changing knowledge.

There were 2 main process on the research:

1) knowledge exchange by using workshop of Tree Diagram to create the suitable model under the Philosophy of Sufficiency Economy by King Rama 9th which offered 7 steps to develop the communities leaders: 1) training/study, 2) changing mind, 4) changing problems to be solutions, 5) using moral, 5) creating team/ planning, 6) doing, and 7) summarizing and developing (Office of the Royal Development Projects Board, 2011, p. 1-32 and Prathumpa, 2013, Interview).

2) Using the created model of 15 activities of implementation in participatory learning activities that the researchers had applied from steps to develop the learning centers by Soisraklang (2013) and Manolai (2013) composed of 1) studying the conditions and problems to define the developing topics, 2) creating team and developing their ability, 3) choosing the areas, 4) using related theories, 5) developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Center, 6) creating research team, 7) planning, 8) planning on the Participation Model, 9) defining the criteria, 10) following the plan, 11) trying to improve the center, 12) assessing, 13) making conclusion, 14) presenting the progress, and 15) supporting by rewards.

Research Instruments

1. The Participation Model between school and community in developing the Self Efficiency Learning Centers was created including its indicator success on construction and efficiency of the instrument discrimination with item total correlation and reliability from Cronbach with using α -Coefficient. The learning achievement test was found with Item Difficulty between .55-.81, Item Discrimination between .24-.81, and Total Reliability at .86

2. The assessment forms during and after using the developing model on the Self Efficiency Learning Centers in the areas

2.1 The assessment forms during using the developing model composed of:

2.1.1 After Action Review (AAR) form on the lessons plan (Plainoi, 2011). The researchers had collected the data after assessment activities with participants in order to follow up the developing progress of the sample group, coordinator, and members continuously.

2.1.2 The Structured Interview form. The data were collected with the sample group in order to follow up the participation of the school and community in developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers at Khoa community, Lao Sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham Province.

2.1.3 The Structured Observation List form. The data were collected at pre-test and post-test.

2.2 The assessment forms after using the developing model composed of:

2.2.1 The learning assessment form with 5 rating scales. The data were separated into 5 topics; 1) sufficiency, 2) reasonability, 3) self-immunity, 4) factors of knowledge, and 5) morals.

2.2.2 the Assessment Form for personal and public practice of Sufficiency Economy.

2.2.3 The questionnaire on the satisfaction of the Participation Model between school and community in developing the Self Efficiency Learning Center by using cutting point with total reliability at .93 and the t-test(Dependent) at 2.30-7.00.

Statistic Used

1. Average, mean, and standard deviation (Sri-saard. 2002)

2. T-test (Dependent), process effectiveness and E1/E2 result, and effectiveness index (Brahmawong, 1994, p. 14-67).

Research results

1. According to the workshop on conditions of Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers in the target area, on October 12, 2014, and Sanyen (2014, November 26) Head of Record of working at Ban Kloa Sa-due Isan School, Lao district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham province, the researchers had exchanged learning with agriculturist leaders, school administrators, and community leaders in Lao sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham Province. The conditions, problems, and requirements from the learning exchange showed that the significant problems of learning management were non sufficiently related, both inside and outside schools, between schools and learning resources centers in the local environment at sub-district level. There was no connection between each concerned group leading to a lack of relationship between schools and the centers on how to correctly use the Philosophy of Sufficiency Economy. The shortage of teachers who can offer learning management as instructors since they had their teachings over workload for the conditions of teachers movement very often occurred that students from different classes even had to gather in the same class. That was the reason why after asking for volunteer participation of schools and community in developing communities' learning resources, there was only Ban Kwoa Sa-due Isan School interested in participating. Therefore, this school attended the project of the Sufficiency Economy Learning Center.

The researchers found that The strong points of the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers were 1) the owners owned their lands to work, 2) workers were the owners' family members, 3) the owners had various techniques in doing mixed agriculture, and 4) the owners had high confidence in practicing new techniques. However, they still needed some developments on sufficient systematic management. The weak points were 1) lacking of planning to pay back their dept, 2) lacking of having households income and payment records, 3) lacking of the centers' facilities such as toilets, or rest seats, 4) lacking of the Sufficiency Economy Learning criteria evaluation, 5) lacking of knowledge, skills, and recognition on using organic fertilizer to decrease the product investment, 6) lacking of readiness and supporters in learning management. Moreover, there were some obstructions that the Sufficiency Economy Learning Center occasionally met; 1) lacking of rain water, 2) lacking of knowledgeable people to transfer indigenous knowledge, 3) unstable households economy, and 4) expensive consumer goods.

The objectives and requirement of the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers were 1) to have mixed agriculture continuously, to decrease the households payment, and to increase the households income, 2) to strengthen the learning activities, and 3) to develop, to study, to exchange knowledge and to decrease the risks.

2. The Participation Model between school and community in developing the centers at Khoa community, Lao Sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham Province was created by using 2 components; 1) 6 steps of participation action research and (2) 15 activities. After the model was investigated by 5 experts, it was found that its levels of feasibility, propriety, and utility were all at the highest levels, except its accuracy which was at high level. The consistency between the model and the learning practice was at the highest level, and its usefulness was at the most benefit level.

3. The usage of the Participatory Model in developing the centers was evaluated by local participants that 1) the efficiency of learning process was 89.62/85.90 as specified criterion, 2) the effectiveness index of overall development in the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers was 0.7494 which indicated that the centers' managers increased their knowledge 74.94 3) the difference scores of the centers' managers, comparing on the pre-test and post-test of knowledge and comprehension in leadership, Sufficiency Economy Philosophy, and knowledge management, were statistically significant at 0.05. 4) the satisfaction on the participation model was at high level.

4. The learning assessment capability on the participation between school and community in development of Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers model was at highest level , (\bar{x} = 4.63), of all 5 topics; 1) sufficiency, 2) reasonability, 3) self-immunity, 4) factors of knowledge, and 5) morals.

The results of using the Participation Model between school and community in developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers at Khoa community, Lao Sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham Province with 2 components was shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: The Participation Model between school and community in developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Center at Khoa community, Lao Sub-district, Kosumphisai district, Maha Sarakham Province

Discussion

1. According to the study of conditions of Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers in the target area, the researchers found that there were 6 Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers in mixed agriculture related to the

study of Leupanya (2012, p. 195-196) who had found 7 sufficiency economy learning centers in the target area and Kumphang (2017, p. 200-202) who had found 6 learning centers in his target area, too. Since The philosophy of Sufficiency Economy from King Rama 9th, of Thailand seem to be the best way to apply to strengthen Thai people life management in balancing their society, Thai villagers enthusiastically took the philosophy to solve their problems successfully that they could establish many Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers in their villages. However, the centers' management needed to be developed systematically in order to be suitable learning resources for schools in accordance with Chantarasombat & Agsonsua (2020, p. 186), Chantarasombat & Sombatsakulkit (2021, p.198) who has been usage the researcher found that were 9 Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers for self-reliance.

2. The model of the Participation Model between school and community in developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers had been investigated by 5 experts that the levels of feasibility, propriety, and utility were at the highest level. With such the sufficient learning management model, successful knowledge appropriately occurred. The usage of the model had its efficiency at 89.62/85.90 as specified criterion, effectiveness index of overall development in Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers at 0.7494 which indicated that the managers of Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers gained more knowledge averagely at 74.94.

3. The suitable with conditions and participants of the model had been proof that it could manage the local participations on their learning usage both to individually and their families in accordance with Chantarasombat & Agsonsua (2020, p. 187-188), Chantarasombat & Sombatsakulkit (2021, p.200-201) who has been proof that it could manage the leaning usage both to individually, families and Sufficiency Economy Learning center.

4. The results from the Participation Model between school and community in developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers shown the capability of doing activities at highest level. Learning management suitably occurred leading to active participations in changing knowledge on thinking, making decision, planning, doing, examining, responding, and gaining. These activities related to the philosophy of King Rama 9th who had stated on cohesion to gather energy for the purposive achievement (Office of the Royal Development Projects Board, 2005, p. 32, and Vasee (2002, p. 21) who had mentioned that participation could offer learning achievement.

Recommendations

1. Recommendations from the results

The developing the Sufficiency Economy Learning Centers should connect local schools and their families as networking of learning.

1.1 There should use the Sufficiency Economy philosophy to record their households income, to plan together, to save money, to thoughtfully do activities, to set leaning management, to be moral and honest to each others.

1.2 Developing participation activities should have 8 steps of thinking together, making decision together, planning together, doing together, examining together, responding together, gaining together and changing knowledge.

1.3 The school learning centers should study from the local centers' local wisdom to apply with the schools' learning centers.

2. Recommendations for further studies

2.1 Should develop this model to further study in other areas.

2.2 Should develop the effective curriculum in the communities for leaders of community, organizations, learning managers with activities.

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